

Jnanadeepa: Pune Journal of Religious Studies

25/4 Oct-Dec 2021, ISSN P-0972-3331 | E-2582-8711 | **49-65**

www.punejournal.in | DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5117987

Stable URL: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5117987>

John Henry Newman and His Untiring Quest for the Truth: The Magisterium and Personal Conscience

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Abstract: Conscience is the living sanctuary in Person. Precisely because we have a moral conscience-, we ought to seek the truth and so shape our choices and our lives accordance with the Truth. John Henry Newman did not write a theological treatise on conscience, but it played a significant role in his life (Autobiographical essay “Apologia Pro vita Sua”). His prayer life, intellect and his conscience led him from the Anglican Church to the Catholic Church. Conscience was for him the guiding light in his life. The uniqueness of his notion of conscience lies in his emphasis on conscience in relation to freedom, responsibility and belief in God. This recast helped to protect the dignity of conscience also in view of the papal dogma on the infallibility of the pope: “Certainly, if I am obliged to bring religion into after-dinner toasts ... I shall drink – to the Pope, if you please – still, to Conscience first, and to the Pope afterwards.”

Keywords: John Henry Newman, Conscience, Dignity of human person, Truth, Existence of God, One Church, papal infallibility.

Cite as: Vaz, Savio. (2021). John Henry Newman and His Untiring Quest for the Truth: The Magisterium and Personal Conscience (Version 1.0). Jnanadeepa: Pune Journal of Religious Studies, Oct-Dec 2021(25/4), **49-65**. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5117987>.

Amidst many voices and noises around us, the mild echo of the conscience is often unheeded. The sacred conscience in each person is an unyielding authority and has Devine purpose. Obeying it means conforming to the will of God and experiencing the freedom.

The Magisterium versus Personal Conscience

The Catholic Church in ninetieth and twentieth Century was struggling, with not only political developments in Europe (aftermath of French Revolution, collapse of Papal States) weakening of ecclesiastical influence, but also to grasp the relation between individual conscience of the faithful and the fidelity to the teaching of the Church (Magisterium). One of the leading historian and ecclesiastical figure embroiled in the conflict between the papal Authority and the personal conscience was the German Priest and Professor Ignaz von Doellinger (1799-1890). He was one of the most learned and influential Scholars of his time and became later a staunch opponent of temporal power of the Pope (Howard, 2017: 1-15). John Henry Newman (1801-1890) and the British Prime Minister William E. Gladstone (1809-1898) were among many his friends. Doellinger found himself caught up in a fierce conflict between his personal conscience and papal authority, between his conviction and Church doctrine. He refused to accept the doctrine of papal infallibility promulgated at the First Vatican Council (Doellinger, 1862), and because of his non-acceptance of the conciliar Doctrine, he was ex-communicated. John Henry Newman remarks over Doellinger: “As to Doellinger ... the case is quite tragic.” Newman showed his solidarity for Doellinger (Ward, 1912: 438-9).

Johann Joseph Ignanz von Doellinger was not just a simple Catholic priest, but a most authoritative and well-versed church historian. His well-articulated opposition to the teaching of papal infallibility bears witness to it (Doellinger, under pseudonym- Janus, 1869). Here he criticizes the notion of papal infallibility and found its promulgation inopportune. It throws light on the integrity of his

personality itself as a man of intellectual integrity and of deep convictions. His commitment to the truth and conscience demanded an enormous price. Doellinger himself gave justification of his position. “Because...if I did so in a question which is for the historical eye perfectly clear and unambiguous, there would then be no longer for me any such thing as historical truth and certainty; I should then have to suppose that my whole life long I had been in a world of dizzy illusion, and that in historical matters I am altogether incapable of distinguishing truth from fable and falsehood (Cited in Sparrow-Simpson, 1909: 324).

The apprehensions regarding the consequences from the new doctrine of the infallibility of the Pope raised doubts and demanded elucidation. The papacy was under sustained attack and many Theologians tried their best to defend the claims of the Church. Unlike Doellinger, John Henry Newman saw the need to explain the relationship between conscience and obedience towards Church authority in a manner, which avoided confrontation and solicited dialogue. He himself was wrestling with the consequences of an exaggerated understanding of papal authority. Deeply stirred over the decision of the Council to define the dogma of the infallibility of the Pope and fearing possible reactions from Catholics and non-Catholics, Newman wrote to his Ordinary of Birmingham, Bishop William B. Ullathorne, expressing his disapproval against defining papal infallibility: “If it is God’s Will that Pope’s Infallibility should be defined, then it is His Blessed Will to throw back the times and the moments of that triumph He has destined for His Kingdom; and I shall feel I have to bow my head to His adorable inscrutable Providence. You have not touched on the subject yourself, but I think you will allow me to express to you my feelings which for the most part I keep to myself” (Letter to the Bishop 28.01.1870, Ward, 1913: 288-289).

For Newman, his interest was not primarily to vindicate the papacy or papal teaching, but much deeper, to explore the Truth from

different angles and understand it in its context. He was not a man of extremes but the apostle of *via media*. Avery Dulles gives a clear assessment and judgment regarding the position of John Henry Newman towards the papal infallibility. “He writes as if caught between two mindsets, unable to choose between them. He is torn by two sets of fears. When he looks at the ultramontane curialists, he speaks almost as a liberal, defending the rights of private judgment and conscience against the harsh impositions of authority. But when he contemplates the rapid spread of infidelity, he rushes to the defense of centralized authority. Thus he is at one moment the ally of Döllinger and the Gallicans and at the next moment the admirer of Cardinal Dechamps and the papalists. He wavers and sometimes contradicts his own previous statements” (Dulles, 1990: 449). Unfortunately, the theology of Newman has been often misinterpreted und distorted. In order avoid false interpretation of his teaching; we must get to his own original words and his authentic teaching. The role of conscience in the moral and spiritual life of Christian is one of the central themes of Newman’s theological research. Then, the person is for him defined by his conscience. No temporal advantages and gains can override the principles of conscience without causing lasting harm to the person.

Vatican I and the Papal Primacy

The First Vatican Council in his dogmatic Constitution on the Church of Christ “*Pastor Aeternus*” defined on 18th July 1870 that: “... we teach and define that is a dogma Divinely revealed that the Roman pontiff when he speaks *ex cathedra*, that is when in discharge of the office of pastor and doctor of all Christians, by virtue of his supreme Apostolic authority, he defines a doctrine regarding faith or morals to be held by the universal Church, by the Divine assistance promised to him in Blessed Peter, is possessed of the infallibility with which the Divine Redeemer willed that his Church should be endowed in defining doctrine regarding faith or morals, and that therefore such definitions of the Roman pontiff are

of themselves, and not from the consent of the church, irreformable” (Ch. 4). Newman lived in a time of great religious and political turmoil. He knew all about political under-currents and felt the brunt of non-Catholic misunderstanding and some Catholic rejection. Amidst all controversies and confrontations, he was guided and led by his unflinching conscience as a natural mode to hear God’s Voice. This same concept of conscience he brought into relation with ecclesiastical authority, which he accepted as divinely ordained to root out errors and face challenges, which were confronted by the Church.

Although the fears and uncertainties regarding the doctrine of infallibility were genuine but not shattering, Doellinger remains unreconciled and is a victim of misunderstanding papal authority and the conscience. Thomas Howard in his Book “The Pope and the Professor” juxtaposes Doellinger with Pope Pius IX. Doellinger considered papalism and in particular the doctrine of papal infallibility counter to the modern, enlightened Christianity, which he represented. In this matter of controversy, a question can be raised: Were the Roman Pontiffs generally against the freedom of conscience? Pope Pius IX spoke in his Encyclical “Quanta cura” 1864 against “liberty of conscience and refers to his predecessor, Pope Gregory XVI., who called it in his encyclical “Mirari vos” 1832 a “deliramentum” (insanity). Pope Gregory XVI condemned the extreme liberalism, which permitted all kinds of groundless, libelous and subversive public opinions, without any legal restrictions. He termed such conception of freedom of conscience as “deliramentum” according to which “freedom of conscience must be asserted und vindicated for everyone whatsoever.” Newman sought to explain the true nature of conscience. The “liberty of conscience” as condemned by “Quanta cura” has not to do with true nature of freedom of conscience, but with the “liberty of self-will”. The Church does not support such an understanding or opinions of the liberty of conscience. Conscience is bound to uphold the truth in the same way the papacy is bound to uphold the truth. Despite the

hopes and fears of the moment, the papal infallibility been specifically invoked only on certain solemn occasions like in 1854 defining the dogma of Mary's Immaculate Conception or in 1950 to define the dogma of her bodily assumption into Heaven. The dogmatic constitution *Lumen gentium* of the Second Vatican Council explicitly reaffirmed the teaching of the First Vatican Council on papal Infallibility (*Lumen gentium*, LG, Art. 25).

The personality of John Henry Newman is an exemplar, shining sign for modern man. He transmitted through his remarkable writings and teachings a perfect example of authenticity, courage and perseverance. He was unmoved through the false charges against him, defended his convictions out of faith and conscience. An interesting aspect of his personal integrity is the connection between conscience and truth. It is a connection, which enables one to detect his personal life of faith and his theological quest. Newman's personal journey to catholic faith is an impressive endorsement of the fundamental conviction of conscience. He sought Truth in religion at all cost and adapted the traditional notion of conscience by emphasizing more the connection of conscience to human freedom, responsibility and relationship to God. To understand Newman's theological understanding of the conscience, we must know his three conversions, which are steps along the spiritual path. The first conversion he had as a young boy and it is a conversion to true faith in the living God. Newman had spiritual experience of God as the living reality. More than natural things Newman recognized that God and the Soul, man's spiritual identity, constitute what is genuinely real.

John Henry Newman: Rome and Not Canterbury the True Church

Arguably, the most renowned convert of the 19th century to Catholic Church is John Henry Newman. At the age of 44, John Henry became a Roman Catholic and was ordained a Roman Catholic priest. Before he graduated from Trinity College, Oxford

and he was an Anglican vicar of St. Mary's University Church. In 1833 John along with few others, initiated a spiritual and doctrinal renewal of Anglican Church, which was known as the "Oxford movement." The Oxford movement was the name given to the endeavours and plans of a group of Anglican Clergymen at Oxford University in 1830s. This Movement sought to restore Catholic faith and practice within the Anglican Church. Its founding members were John Keble (1792-1866) Professor of poetry, Edward Bouverie Pusey (1800-1892) Professor of Hebrew and John Henry Newman, vicar of St. Mary's and fellow of Oriel. To promote their ideas for the renewal of the Anglican Church they preferred a series of publications called "tracts" -hence they were later known as tracterians. They wrote tracts that called the British Protestants back to the historical roots of their faith and urging a more serious attitude toward doctrine and church discipline.

This Anglo-Catholic movement was to move the Church of England away from Protestantism towards a middle way "via media" between Anglicanism and Roman Catholicism. The main conviction shared by the movement was that England had lost the Faith of the Ancient Church Fathers and that it needed a (second Reformation) a comeback to the original Church. While still in Oxford, Newman questioned his own spiritual path within the Anglican Church. He prayed for light and guidance and followed a strict religious life. In his eagerness to find the true Nature of the one Church, Newman started to study the development of Christian doctrine. He started with the Church fathers and came to quick conclusion: "To be deep in history is to cease to be Protestant." In his book "An Essay on the Development of Christian Doctrine", he found the living connection between the apostolic faith and the Catholic Church. The Catholic Church is the continuation of the community founded by Jesus. Newman begins there explaining how true development in doctrine occur. He presents the unfolding of the teaching from the apostolic to the present time. Church has tried to safeguard the true teaching of Christ. The Catholic doctrine is the

evolving of the same faith, which was in seminal form and has now blossomed into doctrine and dogmas. There is no corruption or innovation in the teaching of the Church. The path to such a profound understanding was triggered by his conscience, which pondered seriously on the nature of the Church. In order to understand his decision to leave the Anglican Church, we must know the nature of conscience according to Newman.

Conscience the Path to Truth

Newman chose the inscription on his grave, “*Ex umbris et imaginibus in veritatem*” – “Out of shadows and images into truth.” That was truly his life’s maxim. He dedicated his life in searching and following the Truth and was fully committed to it, no matter what price he had to pay. His decision to join the Catholic Church costed him not only his position at Oxford University, but also damaged his friendships and reputation (Schockenhoff, 2003: 122-143). Some Catholics and many Anglicans became distrustful of him. However, his passion for Truth gained him new friends and companions, but above all, he valued to be at home in the true Church of Christ. Admittedly, “what is truth?” (Jn 18,38) This question posed to Jesus by Pilate continues to echo until today. Newman was restless and he sought to answer, what is truth. In his famous Novel titled *Callista: A Tale of the Third Century*, speaks out one of the Characters: “The Truth! ... What is truth?” (Newman, 1901: 249). Truth is an indispensable guide to men; it acts like a compass in his moral and faith life.

Newman saw a deeper connection between Conscience and Truth. His numerous statements about conscience are most striking and relevant texts, which he left for us. Not by chance, he is called *Doctor conscientiae* or teacher of conscience. The most conclusive certainty for the existence of God for Newman was in the testimony of conscience and not through the argument of logic (Boekraad-Tristram, 1961). Newman laid emphasis on the certainty of his own existence in feeling, experiencing and sensing. He found and

experienced God in the voice of his own conscience, a supreme Governor and Judge, which confirmed the existence of God. From this basic connection between Conscience and Truth, we can see the consequence in his personal life of faith and in his theological understanding. No other influence can be traced in his vivid search for truth and his fundamental conviction, “conscience as the advocate of truth in the innermost part of the human person” (Geissler, 2012: 1). If the human conscience is of paramount importance then it cannot be self-sufficient and arbitrary, hence, it calls for lifelong obedience to objective truth.

In his serious analysis of the phenomenon of conscience, Newman differentiates two functions or dimensions of the same conscience: namely, moral sense and sense of duty. He describes the sublime-character of conscience in a magnificent way: “The rule and measure of duty is not utility, nor expedience, nor the happiness of the greatest number, nor State convenience, nor fitness, order, and the pulchrum. Conscience is not a long-sighted selfishness, nor a desire to be consistent with oneself, but it is a messenger from Him, who, both in nature and in grace, speaks to us behind a veil, and teaches and rules us by His representatives. Conscience is the aboriginal Vicar of Christ, a prophet in its informations, a monarch in its peremptoriness, a priest in its blessings and anathemas, and, even though the eternal priesthood throughout the Church could cease to be, in it the sacerdotal principle would remain and would have a sway” (Newman, 1896: 248f.) The understanding and role of conscience goes beyond knowledge to action. It is an authority, which inspires to act.

In his spiritual autobiographical book *Apologia Pro vita Sua (A defence of one’s own life)*, Newman tells that his search brought him the right home for his faith. In Chapter 10 of his book *Grammar of Assent*, Newman sums up the importance of having an active conscience: “Conscience is nearer to me than any other means of knowledge. And as it is given to me, so also is it given to others;

and being carried about by every individual in his own breast, and requiring nothing besides itself, it is thus adapted for the communication to each separately of that knowledge which is most momentous to him individually,— adapted for the use of all classes and conditions of men, for high and low, young and old, men and women independently of books, of educated reasoning, of physical knowledge, or of philosophy. Conscience, too, teaches us, not only that God is, but He is; it provides for the mind a real image of Him, as a medium of worship; it gives us a rule of right and wrong, as being His rule, and a code of moral duties” (Newman, 1958: 390). Like Newman, everyone has to form his conscience, examine it and obey it under all circumstances.

Conscience: A Path to True Faith

Another decisive step in the life of Newman, which is a consequence of his understanding of conscience, is obviously the obedience to God as the Redeemer and the quest for the fullness of truth in the one Church of Christ. The question of the one Church of Christ is ultimately connected to the question of Salvation. According to Newman, the obedience to conscience form an “*organum investigandi* given us for gaining religious truth, and which would lead the mind by an infallible succession from the rejection of atheism to theism, and from theism to Christianity, and from Christianity to Evangelical Religion, and from these to Catholicity” (Newman, 1874: 499). It is interesting because Newman before his conversion to Catholic Church bore an anti-Roman sentiment, which was common in the Anglican Church. He had warned his faithful about the danger of Rome like that of a plague. No doubt, Newman lived in a time of mutual suspicion and antagonism between the two Churches.

The right belief in God enlightened by the obedience to conscience brought him to realisation of the true Church, to a spiritual home. The conscience is for him the connecting principle between Creator and his Creature. In his *Apologia pro vita sua*, Newman says

candidly: “I am a Catholic by virtue of my believing in a God; and if I am asked why I believe in a God, I answer that it is because I believe in myself, for I feel it impossible to believe in my own existence (and of that fact I am quite sure) without believing also in the existence of Him, who lives as a Personal, All-seeing, All-judging Being in my conscience” (Newman, 1865: 198). The conscience of the person becomes the highest moral law and Newman had again discreetly solved the problem between conscience and obedience to the Church’s Magisterium during the time of papal infallibility doctrine. The theme of conscience lies at the heart of “The Letter to the Duke of Norfolk.” Newman wrote this letter in the wake of the First Vatican Council as a response to the charge of the then British Prime Minister William Gladstone, in light of the First Vatican Council’s adoption of the new dogma, Catholics would have no mental freedom, being captives and slaves of the Pope. Newman explained to the Duke of Norfolk that Catholics in England would continue to be faithful subjects of the Crown after the doctrine of papal infallibility (Doctrine of infallibility, First Vatican Council 1869-70). Catholics remain masters of their conscience and not the Pope. The oft-quoted saying of Newman, “if I am obliged to bring religion into after-dinner toasts, (which indeed does not seem quite the thing) I shall drink—to the Pope, if you please—still, to Conscience first, and to the Pope afterwards.” It is a clear testimony, which states that our Catholic understanding of conscience is in no way a blind obedience to the Magisterium but one based on a respect to personal conscience guided by faith (Zimmermann, 2005: 289-317).

Newman became a great inspiration for the “White Rose Resistance” against Hitler in Germany. Many Newman’s ideas of conscience translated in German language helped Hans and Sophie Scholl to fight against the Nazi-regime. Hans and Sophie Scholl were brother and sister. As Students, they were arrested and executed after being found guilty of distributing anti-war, anti-Hitler leaflets at the University of Munich. They were both active

within the White Rose non-violent resistance group. Theodor Haeckel, philosopher and culture historian, who guided the “White Rose”, became Catholic after translating Newman’s book *Grammar of Assent*. The Second Vatican Council has assimilated many elements of Newman’s understanding of conscience. “*Gaudium et spes*”, Article 16 states: “In the depths of his conscience, man detects a law which he does not impose upon himself, but which holds him to obedience” (also John Paul II. 1993: 54-56). Similarly, we read in the Declaration “*Dignitatis Humanae* Art. 3: “that the highest norm of human life is God’s divine law – eternal, objective, and universal.” In addition, “Wherefore every man has the duty, and therefore the right, to seek the truth ... in order that he may with prudence form for himself right and true judgments of conscience.”

One True Church

Conscience as creative Principle of the Religion expresses itself through the sense of duty. For Newman conscience is the echo of God’s voice and not the voice of God. The experience of God in conscience calls for a response. We can notice the compatibility of his convictions with his proceedings. The moment he realises, that the Catholic Church is the bearer of the truth, he leaves his old Church in which he grew and lived. The greatness of the person lies in his openness to the truth, which God communicates to him (Allsopp, 1992: 192-208). He sought truth in religion and that at all cost. He saw the important source of doctrinal and spiritual unity provided by the bishop of Rome, which was lacking in Anglican Church. The Witness of the Church Fathers, whom he had extensively studied, urged him to join the Church of Rome, which had the fullness of Antiquity, Apostolic Succession, Universality and Holiness. In his most influential Work “*An Essay on the Development of Christian Doctrine*, painstakingly details the manner in which Christian Doctrine has developed over time. Digging deep into the history of the early Church Newman is overwhelmed with the certainty and without doubt, that the

Protestant position lacks a solid basis, and that the Catholic Church is the true Church founded by Christ. Having studied the Fathers of the Church, he felt the depth of faith and there was no other better preference than to crossover to Catholic Church. Indeed, this book is more on the defence of the Roman Catholic Church and her claim to be one true Church. It is one of the most famous presentation in defence of the Church by the most noted converts. He notes "... the doctrines of which the present Catholic religion consist are prima facie the correct, true, faithful, legitimate development of the doctrines which preceded them, and not their corruption" (Newman, 1845: 202). Truth was his passion. The same Truth Newman found in becoming Catholic, he defended against the relativism of the 19th century.

The more we occupy ourselves with the writings of Newman, the more we see the depth of his theological reflections and convictions. Great parallels can be drawn in the lives of the two great Saints of English Reformation, John Fisher (1469-1535), Thomas More (1478-1535) and John Henry Newman. John Fisher and Thomas More (A play from Robert Bolt titled "A Man for All Seasons", 1960 and the motion film with the same title 1966- depicting the life of Sir Thomas More) were Martyrs of conscience. Both had to die because they refused to accept King Henry VIII as supreme Head of the Church of England and for upholding the Catholic Church's doctrine of papal primacy (Mann, 2017). Thomas More, the Lord Chancellor and was executed by Henry VIII for his refusal to sign the first succession act. His famous words: "The king's good servant, but God's first." John Cardinal Fisher was the Bishop from Rochester, he was decapitated while he refused to accept the second marriage of Henry VIII. John Fisher and Thomas More willingly accepted the execution than to betray their conscience and the Catholic Faith. The integrity of their conscience remained intact throughout their lives, trials and condemnation. Peter Berglar titled his book over Thomas More; "A Lonely Voice Against the Power of the State," gives reason why he deliberately chose this subtitle.

He writes, “Thomas More stood alone, first, because conscience is something altogether personal, but above all because those who follow their conscience often are few. Where circumstances require it, obedience to conscience also implies the capacity for steadfastness in the face of an overwhelming majority that thinks or decides otherwise” (Berglar, 2009: vii). The consequence of following the conscience led John Fisher and Thomas More to Martyrdom, they died defending the inalienable dignity of human conscience and John Henry led the conscience to Catholic Faith. He is not a Martyr, but had to suffer injustice and false accusations. They were persons of moral integrity, witnesses of the primacy of truth and defenders of human conscience. They loved the Catholic teaching. According to great Irish author James Joyce, whom Newman was the greatest literary writer, said of Newman, “nobody has ever written English prose that can be compared with that of a tiresome footling little Anglican parson who afterwards became a prince of the only true Church”.

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Article received: March 28, 2021

Accepted: April 4, 2021

Word count: 5020

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